

A Study on Impact of AI Chatbots on Consumer Purchase Intention with reference to online shopping in Kheda District

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Abstract

This Study examines the role of AI chatbots in the evolving E-commerce sector of Kheda District (Gujarat) and its impact on Consumer Purchase Intentions based on their demographics. This study investigates the impact of AI chatbots on consumer purchase intention in the context of online shopping in Kheda District, using a sample size of 68 respondents. The findings reveal that there are no significant differences in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty, and conversion impact between males and females or across different education levels and occupations. However, a notable difference in brand loyalty is observed between the age groups of 18 to 30 and 30 to 40. While the overall relationship between trust in chatbots' recommendations and purchases is not statistically significant according to Pearson Chi-Square and Likelihood Ratio tests, a significant linear trend suggests that increased trust in chatbot recommendations is associated with higher purchase likelihood. Furthermore, significant differences in both influence to purchase and likelihood to purchase are found across varying levels of interaction frequency, indicating that interaction frequency plays a crucial role in shaping these variables. This research highlights the importance of interaction frequency and age-specific strategies in enhancing brand loyalty and consumer engagement in the e-commerce landscape of Kheda District.

Key Words: AI Chatbots, Purchase Intentions, Consumer Behaviour, E-commerce

Introduction

The rise of online shopping has drastically changed the way that consumers make purchase decisions, and this is quite different from traditional shopping. Traditional shopping usually imposes several limitations on consumers, such as geographical constraints, time limitations, and a restricted choice of products. In addition, the in-store shopping experience is sometimes faced with long queues, crowded stores, and the unavailability of products that one wants. Online shopping, in comparison offers many advantages: it is convenient, offers a wide variety of products, and one can shop from the comfort of home.

E-commerce businesses face various challenges, from improving customer service and personalization in the absence of physical contact with a sales representative to enhancing overall experience. In e-commerce, chatbots can serve as an alternate solution for online shopping by filling these gaps in interaction and thereby helping the shoppers navigate through a given site, recommending products or aiding in various purchasing phases. Most AI chatbots built for this particular purpose rely on natural language processing and machine learning algorithms, so they are conceived to simulate a human-like conversation.

The use of AI chatbots in e-commerce sites has brought a significant effect on consumer buying intentions in the context of Kheda District. Giving instant answers and personalized recommendations, AI chatbots significantly help in improving customer experiences, building trust, and increasing consumer satisfaction. These chatbots are also quite effective at handling multiple interactions with customers simultaneously, thereby reducing wait times and increasing the efficiency of the e-commerce business. Additionally, the ability of AI chatbots to provide the exact information sought after by the consumer has helped to remove the fear of making a wrong product selection and purchasing decision, resulting in improved conversions.

The objective of this research is to find out the impact of AI chatbots on consumer purchase intention with reference to online shopping in Kheda District. This research tries to provide insights on how e-commerce can further be improved by AI-driven technologies such as chatbots through an examination of the gaps in online shopping experiences and the effects brought by the integration of AI chatbots. The study of the ability of AI chatbots in converting website browsing into purchase decisions is one of the main considerations of this study. Online retailers can consider these factors in the optimization of their platforms to create a better, more engaging, and effective shopping experience for customers with the help of AI Chatbots.

Review of Literature

The impact of AI chatbots on consumer purchase intention with reference to online shopping in Kheda District, is a matter of concern that has been reflected in several studies. It is because AI chatbots facilitate the improvement of user experience, trust, and satisfaction, which has a direct correlation with purchasing. The subsequent sections explain the details of this effect.

Better User Experience: AI chatbots increase the efficiency of product choice, thereby leading to an increased shopping experience (Rahevar & Darji, 2024). Rapid service is delivered, reducing the number of days taken to respond and increasing consumer satisfaction (Lei & Cai, 2024). Engagement in interactive communication with a chatbot that responds based on an individual's needs increases participation (Dai & Liu, 2024). Perceived usefulness and ease of use of chatbots positively affect customer attitudes and behaviours (Bui, Thanh, & Khoa, 2021). “Factors such as perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, innovativeness, perceived information quality, and perceived customisation affect users' intention to use Chatbots.” (Goli, Sahu, Bag, & Dhamija, 2023)

Trust and Transparency: The ethical application of AI-based chatbots leads consumers to build trust, which is also required for the purchase motivation (Dai & Liu, 2024). Transparency of a chatbot's activity enhances users' perceptions of it (Kumari, 2024). The study done by (Yun & Park, 2022) examined the effect of chatbots on retention rates of consumer.

Emotional Connection: The positive emotional relationship created through the interactions with the chatbots strongly leads to purchase intention (Lei & Cai, 2024). The emotional bonding of users to the chatbots maximizes satisfaction and loyalty (butt & hussan, 2023). The study of (Yun & Park, 2022) also shows that Chatbots with emotion words positively impact customer satisfaction.

Cultural Context and Adaptation: Effectiveness may vary across different cultural contexts, as has been found in comparative studies of Turkey and Azerbaijan. The key to optimizing chatbot interactions in Kheda District lies in understanding local consumer preferences (Celik, et al., 2022).

Research Gap

While studies emphasize the need to understand local consumer preferences (Celik et al., 2022) and other variables associated to chatbots, there is limited research regarding the unique cultural factors and perspective of people towards AI Chatbots in Kheda District. There is a need of more studies emphasizing over consumer purchase intention which can add value via analysing certain variables as found out through literature review.

Research Methodology

Objectives of study

1. To Study relation between AI Chatbots and Consumer's Purchase Intention with reference to online shopping in Kheda District
2. To Study the Impact of AI Chatbots on Consumer's Purchase Intention with reference to online shopping in Kheda District.

Hypothesis

H01: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty and conversion impact based on Demographic profile (Gender, Education, Age, Occupation).

H02: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty and conversion impact in different regions of Kheda District.

H03: There is no relationship between Trust in Chatbots' recommendation and purchase based on that.

H04: There is no significant difference in Influence to purchase across different levels of Interaction Frequency.

Research Design

Descriptive research Design was adopted to analyse relationships and trends among the selected sample.

Sampling plan

Non-Probability Convenience Sampling method was used to select respondents for the study. The sample size of the current study was 68 respondents across Kheda District.

Data Collection and Respondents

The data collection was done through a **structured questionnaire**. There were two parts to the survey questionnaire. The first half of the survey contains demographic data from respondents, while the second contains structured questionnaires covering relevant variables. The survey gathered data from 68 respondents across different regions of Kheda District via convenience method.

Table 1. Demographic details.

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	26	38.2
	Male	42	61.8
	Total	68	100
Age			
	18 to 30	50	73.5
	30 to 40	10	14.7
	40 to 50	3	4.4
	above 50	3	4.4
	Below 18	2	2.9
	Total	68	100
city			
	Rural	24	35.3
	Semi-urban	13	19.1
	Urban	31	45.6
	Total	68	100
Education			
	Bachelor's	30	44.1
	Doctorate	3	4.4
	Higher education	11	16.2
	Masters	24	35.3
	Total	68	100
Occupation			
	Employed	26	38.2
	Home Maker	3	4.4
	Self Employed	6	8.8
	Student	33	48.5
	Total	68	100

Data interpretation and discussion

H_{01.1}: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty, and conversion impact between Male and Female.

		Independent Samples Test									
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Significance		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						One-Sided p	Two-Sided p			Lower	Upper
Consumer_Satisfaction_1	Equal variances assumed	.274	.602	1.476	66	.072	.145	.408	.277	-.144	.961
	Equal variances not assumed			1.541	60.226	.064	.129	.408	.265	-.122	.939
Brand_Trust_1	Equal variances assumed	1.911	.171	.622	66	.268	.536	.156	.250	-.344	.655
	Equal variances not assumed			.671	64.424	.252	.504	.156	.232	-.307	.619
Brand_Loyalty_1	Equal variances assumed	3.162	.080	.013	66	.495	.990	.004	.278	-.552	.559
	Equal variances not assumed			.014	64.065	.494	.989	.004	.259	-.513	.521
Conversion_impact_1	Equal variances assumed	1.352	.249	1.168	66	.123	.247	.308	.263	-.218	.834
	Equal variances not assumed			1.242	62.737	.110	.219	.308	.248	-.188	.803

Based on the Independent t test results we can observe that all the p-values(significant) are greater than 0.05, indicating that we fail to reject the null hypothesis for all the variables.

H_{01.2}: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty, and conversion impact between Education levels.

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Consumer_Satisfaction_1	Between Groups	7.448	3	2.483	2.081	.111
	Within Groups	76.361	64	1.193		
	Total	83.809	67			
Brand_Loyalty_1	Between Groups	.410	3	.137	.107	.956
	Within Groups	81.648	64	1.276		
	Total	82.059	67			
Brand_Trust_1	Between Groups	1.389	3	.463	.453	.716
	Within Groups	65.361	64	1.021		
	Total	66.750	67			
Conversion_impact_1	Between Groups	3.965	3	1.322	1.190	.321
	Within Groups	71.094	64	1.111		
	Total	75.059	67			

Upon examination of ANOVA results it can be seen that all variables have p-values grater than 0.05 which in fact says that we fail to reject null hypothesis for all variables.

H_{01.3}: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust brand loyalty and conversion impact in different Age Groups.

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Consumer_Satisfaction_1	Between Groups	9.995	4	2.499	2.133	.087
	Within Groups	73.813	63	1.172		
	Total	83.809	67			
Brand_Loyalty_1	Between Groups	14.072	4	3.518	3.260	.017
	Within Groups	67.987	63	1.079		
	Total	82.059	67			
Brand_Trust_1	Between Groups	6.170	4	1.542	1.604	.184
	Within Groups	60.580	63	.962		
	Total	66.750	67			
Conversion_impact_1	Between Groups	9.012	4	2.253	2.149	.085
	Within Groups	66.047	63	1.048		
	Total	75.059	67			

BRAND LOYALTY			Post hoc				
Multiple Comparisons							
Tukey HSD							
Dependent Variable	(I) Age_1	(J) Age_1	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Brand_Loyalty_1	18 to 30	30 to 40	1.140*	0.36	0.019	0.13	2.15
		40 to 50	-0.127	0.617	1	-1.86	1.61
		above 50	0.54	0.617	0.905	-1.19	2.27
		Below 18	-0.96	0.749	0.703	-3.06	1.14
	30 to 40	18 to 30	-1.140*	0.36	0.019	-2.15	-0.13
		40 to 50	-1.267	0.684	0.354	-3.19	0.65
		above 50	-0.6	0.684	0.904	-2.52	1.32
		Below 18	-2.1	0.805	0.081	-4.36	0.16
	40 to 50	18 to 30	0.127	0.617	1	-1.61	1.86
		30 to 40	1.267	0.684	0.354	-0.65	3.19
		above 50	0.667	0.848	0.934	-1.72	3.05
		Below 18	-0.833	0.948	0.904	-3.5	1.83
above 50	18 to 30	-0.54	0.617	0.905	-2.27	1.19	
	30 to 40	0.6	0.684	0.904	-1.32	2.52	
	40 to 50	-0.667	0.848	0.934	-3.05	1.72	
	Below 18	-1.5	0.948	0.514	-4.16	1.16	
Below 18	18 to 30	0.96	0.749	0.703	-1.14	3.06	
	30 to 40	2.1	0.805	0.081	-0.16	4.36	
	40 to 50	0.833	0.948	0.904	-1.83	3.5	
	above 50	1.5	0.948	0.514	-1.16	4.16	

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

It can be seen here that variables like consumer satisfaction, brand trust and conversion impact have p-values greater than 0.05 which leads to failure of rejecting null hypothesis.

Whereas, Brand Loyalty has 0.017 as result which is lower than 0.05 significance value, it can be said that for Brand Loyalty there is a difference between Age groups.

Upon further Post hoc analysis with Tukey, researcher could conclude that there is a difference between 18 to 30 and 30 to 40 age groups in terms of Brand Loyalty as they have 0.019 significant value which is less than 0.05.

H_{01.4}: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust brand loyalty and conversion impact based on occupation.

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Consumer_Satisfaction_1	Between Groups	1.409	3	.470	.365	.779
	Within Groups	82.400	64	1.287		
	Total	83.809	67			
Brand_Loyalty_1	Between Groups	2.339	3	.780	.626	.601
	Within Groups	79.720	64	1.246		
	Total	82.059	67			
Brand_Trust_1	Between Groups	1.869	3	.623	.615	.608
	Within Groups	64.881	64	1.014		
	Total	66.750	67			
Conversion_impact_1	Between Groups	.582	3	.194	.167	.918
	Within Groups	74.477	64	1.164		
	Total	75.059	67			

Based on the derived ANOVA results, there is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty, and conversion impact based on occupation. All the p-values are greater than 0.05, indicating that we fail to reject the null hypothesis for all the variables.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty and conversion impact in different regions of Kheda District.

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Consumer_Satisfaction_1	Between Groups	4.354	2	2.177	1.781	.177
	Within Groups	79.455	65	1.222		
	Total	83.809	67			
Brand_Loyalty_1	Between Groups	1.560	2	.780	.630	.536
	Within Groups	80.498	65	1.238		
	Total	82.059	67			
Brand_Trust_1	Between Groups	2.556	2	1.278	1.294	.281
	Within Groups	64.194	65	.988		
	Total	66.750	67			
Conversion_impact_1	Between Groups	4.585	2	2.293	2.115	.129
	Within Groups	70.474	65	1.084		
	Total	75.059	67			

Based on above results, there are no significant differences in consumer satisfaction, brand loyalty, brand trust, and conversion impact across different regions of Kheda District. All the p-values are greater than 0.05, indicating that we fail to reject the null hypothesis for all the variables. Therefore, it can be concluded that regional differences in Kheda District do not significantly affect these consumer metrics.

H₀₃: There is no relationship between Trust in Chatbots' recommendation and purchase based on that.

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.724	4	0.068
Likelihood Ratio	8.867	4	0.064
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.744	1	0.029
N of Valid Cases	68		

- The **Pearson Chi-Square** and **Likelihood Ratio** tests suggest that there is no statistically significant relationship between Trust in Chatbots' recommendation and purchase based on that, as the p-values are greater than 0.05. The **Linear-by-Linear Association** test indicates a significant linear relationship between Trust in Chatbots' recommendation and purchase based on that, as the p-value is less than 0.05.

So however, the overall relationship may not be significant according to the Pearson Chi-Square and Likelihood Ratio tests, there is evidence of a significant linear trend. This says that as trust in the chatbot’s recommendation increases, there is a corresponding increase in the likelihood of purchase.

H04: There is no significant difference in Influence to Purchase across different levels of Interaction Frequency.

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Influence_to_Purchase_1	Between Groups	27.973	4	6.993	6.966	<.001
	Within Groups	63.247	63	1.004		
	Total	91.221	67			
Likelihood_to_purchase_1	Between Groups	19.583	4	4.896	5.328	<.001
	Within Groups	57.887	63	0.919		
	Total	77.471	67			

Based on the above results both **Influence to Purchase** and **Likelihood to Purchase** show significant differences across different levels of Interaction Frequency. The p-values for both variables are less than 0.001, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that Interaction Frequency has a significant impact on both Influence to Purchase and Likelihood to Purchase.

Conclusion

Based on the analyses, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in consumer satisfaction, brand trust, brand loyalty, and conversion impact between males and females or across different education levels and occupations. On the other hand, there is a significant difference in brand loyalty between the 18 to 30 and 30 to 40 age groups. Moreover, even though the overall relationship between trust in chatbots' recommendations and purchases is not significant based on Pearson Chi-Square and Likelihood Ratio tests, a significant linear trend indicates that increasing trust in chatbot recommendations corresponds to increasing purchase likelihood. Lastly, both influence to purchase and likelihood to purchase present significant differences across different levels of interaction frequency, therefore it can be concluded that interaction frequency significantly impacts the variables.

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